

tested to determine drought tolerance.

Seeds of each variety were drilled in rainfed fields on 31 Mar 1983 in 5-m-long rows in 3 replications. Stand establishment, drought damage, drought recovery ability, and phenotypic acceptability were recorded 21, 45, 81, and 133 days after seeding (DS). From 21 to 45 DS the plot received 7 mm precipitation. Maximum air and soil temperature ranged from 31.6 to 41.3°C and 34.7 to 48.3°C.

Twenty entries had a drought score of 9 at 45 DS. Eleven entries, including the susceptible check, died during the vegetative period. Pureline selection NC487/77 and hybrid lines CN506-147-2-1 and CN506-147-14-2 (IR30/LMN111//IR1514A-E660) performed better than the resistant check. Jalaplaba, Jaladhi 2, Jaladhi 3, and Janki, all pureline selections, had a high level of drought tolerance (see table). □

TABLE CONTINUED

Entry	Initial stand establishment, 21 DS	Drought tolerance, 45 DS	Recovery, 81 DS	Height (cm), 133 DS	Phenotypic acceptability 133 DS
NC488/78	3.6	6.3	5	71.4	4.3
Achra 108/1	3.6	5	3.6	77.5	3.6
Jalaplaba	2.3	2.3	3	77.8	2.6
FR13A	5.6	7	6.3	63.8	6.3
Jaladhi 1	6.3	6.3	5	75.9	5.6
Jaladhi 2	4.3	3.6	3	83.2	3
Jaladhi 3	3	1.6	3	95.8	2.6
Janki (C64-117)	3	1.6	3	87.5	2.6
Tilokkachari	6.3	6.3	7	74.5	6.3
<i>New varieties</i>					
CN506-147-2-1	3	3	2.3	83.3	2.3
CN506-147-14-2	3	5	3	52.8	2.3
CN683-1	5.6	5	5	80.5	3.6
FPAR 7809	5.6	5	4.3	50.1	5
<i>Resistant check</i>					
Dular	5	3.6	3	102.5	2.6
Salumpikit	8.3	9	8.3	58.7	8.3
<i>Susceptible check</i>					
IR20	9	9	9	28.5	9
Rainfall (mm)	105.9	7.0	116.1		210.5

^a1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. Three replications. DS = days after sowing.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Plant height and growth duration at increased water depths

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Popular semidwarfs were compared with tall varieties in duration and plant height at 55 and 74 cm water depths. Thirty-

day-old seedlings were transplanted during the last week of June. Nitrogen was applied in 2 equal splits to supply 40 kg N/ha during tillering stage. Plots were flooded 45 days after planting and water level was maintained for 3 months, until the first week of November.

Semidwarfs generally showed greater increase in plant height (28-36 cm) than

intermediate and tall (18-34 cm) varieties. MTU16, the traditional deepwater variety, increased 16 cm at 55-cm depth, and 40 cm at 75-cm depth. Flowering duration was delayed by 4-13 days for semidwarfs and 0-8 days for intermediate and tall varieties. Semidwarf varieties had weak stems and lodged at the 75-cm water depth. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Himalaya 1 and Himalaya 2 — two new semidwarf, cold-tolerant rices for Himachal Pradesh, India

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Fifty percent of the rice area of Himachal Pradesh is at altitudes higher than 900 m.

Cold temperatures during flowering reduce rice yields.

Himalaya 1 and Himalaya 2, semidwarf indicas released in 1982, can be successfully cultivated up to 1,550 m altitudes. Himalaya 1, the experimental line HPU734, is a very early maturing selection from IR579 (IR8/Tadukan). It is recommended for low, mid, and high hills. Himalaya 2, the experimental line

HPU71, is an early maturing selection from Pusa 33 (Improved sabarmati/Ratna). It is recommended for low and mid hills up to 1,300 m.

Himalaya 1 is high yielding, cold tolerant, and blast resistant. It yields an average 3.9 t/ha — 26, 15, and 3% more than IR579, China 988, or Himdhan (Table 1). It has long, slender, translucent grains with good cooking quality.